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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE REVOLUTIONIZING OF TERTIARY EDUCATION MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIA: CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

Abdulrasheed Olowoselu

Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: rasheedolowoselu@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT

Educational systems are being revolutionized by artificial intelligence (AI) globally, which is providing new models for inclusive, data-driven, and effective management of tertiary institutions. AI offers a chance to rethink management structures and operational procedures in tertiary education in Nigeria. Conversely, tertiary education faces numerous challenges ranging from inadequate resources, lack of proper funding and technological inefficiencies. The study discusses the potential of AI to transform Nigerian tertiary education affirming on national and global justifications. This study further explores conceptual clarifications of AI and roles of AI in tertiary education management. An important aspect of this study hinges on the discussion of practical challenges of AI management and outlining solutions to proper management of AI in tertiary institution. The study concluded that AI adoption has the potential in transforming tertiary education in Nigeria..

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Tertiary Education, Management

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, tertiary education is essential to the growth of the nation's human capital development. However, its performance has been restricted by structural challenges. New opportunities for updating educational institutions and creating more responsive, transparent and effective systems presented by the development of artificial intelligence (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019; Elliott, 2019). Higher education institutions can move from manual to more efficient operations backed by artificial intelligence (AI) for automation in data analytics and AI-driven technologies (Boyd & Holton, 2018; Tanveer, Hassan, & Bhaumik, 2020). Meanwhile, in some tertiary institutions, there are technological challenges that frequently impede procedural management of student registration, result computation, and transcript issuance (Ayanwale et al., 2024; Shiohira, 2021). These tasks can be completed more easily with less human involvement by AI-powered systems. In addition to cutting operating expenses and enhances the quality of services provided to both employees and students (Gohil, 2023; Challoumis, 2024a). Predictive analytics can also be utilized to forecast enrollment trends, manage workloads, and optimize class scheduling that contribute to improved institutional planning and resource allocation (Jambol et al., 2025; Liu et al., 2024).

AI technologies provide strong tools for individualized learning beyond administration. Students received individualized academic support based on their unique learning styles, performance history, and progress using chatbots,

adaptive learning platforms, and intelligent tutoring systems (Yadav & Shrawankar, 2025). AI systems are able to identify students with learning challenges in courses and suggest specific resources with academic advisors for help (Cain, 2023; Wong et al., 2020). Meanwhile, in order to ease the strain on administrative system in the tertiary institutions, virtual assistants can also offer 24hours assistance with frequently asked questions regarding registration, fees and other students campus services (Tedre et al., 2021; Yue et al., 2025). Institutions should improve on academic results, increase student retention and promote a more student learning-centered approach through implementing AI in teaching and learning processes (Southworth et al., 2023; Lytras et al., 2024).

Administratively, AI has the capacity to evaluate large amounts of data with the potential to uphold accountability and data management in higher education institutions (Challoumis, 2024b; Hutson, 2024). AI systems should give education administrators comprehensive control on key performance indicators such as staff productivity, budget utilization, research output and students' self-esteem through analyzing data from several departments in the institutions (Tanveer et al., 2020; Miao et al., 2021). Conversely, AI promote prudent financial management, records enhanced admissions procedures, assist internal and external auditing with the possibility of fostering institutional integrity and openness (Tanveer et al., 2020; Miao et al., 2021).

Essentially, AI portends challenges in numbers of issues that need to be resolved to guarantee it successful and fairness during integration into Nigerian higher education (Olowoselu, 2025). Deficits in school infrastructure such as unstable electricity supplies, poor internet access and outdated computer systems posed as major challenges especially to institutions that are located in rural areas and underfunded (Igbokwe, 2023). In addition, there is lack of effective regulations governing the ethical use of AI in education, as well as a paucity of qualified specialist to oversee the AI systems (Lampou, 2023; Ogunode et al., 2023). Strategic investments in faculty training, digital infrastructure, and regulatory frameworks are necessary to get over these challenges. International cooperation, pilot projects, and public-private partnerships can all promote innovation and hasten adoption in tertiary institutions (Igbokwe, 2023; Wang et al., 2024).

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS

The concept artificial intelligence (AI) describes computer programs created to carry out tasks that normally calls for human cognitive capacities, like language comprehension, learning, problem-solving, and decision-making. AI includes technology like as chatbots, facial recognition, natural language processing (NLP), predictive analytics, and robotic process automation in the context of educational management (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019). Higher education institutions are incorporating these tools more frequently in order to streamline administrative procedures, improve decision-making and customize students' assistance. AI has been use in education for curriculum development, resource optimization, administrative automation and predictive students' performance tracking (Southworth et al., 2023; Miao et al., 2021). AI-enabled technologies to assist administrators in identifying students at-risk in most developed nations. Although recent studies shown that, colleges in Nigeria are becoming more interested in implementing smart technologies in their management and administrative processes (Fabunmi et al., 2025; Igbokwe, 2023).

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming a key component of educational modernization on a global scale. Administrative automation, curriculum design, resource optimization, and predicted student performance tracking are the managerial roles of AI in an institution (Southworth et al., 2023; Miao et al., 2021). AI-powered tools can track student conduct and academic achievement, assisting teachers and administrators in identifying students who may be at risk of

dropping out of school. Similarly, learning management systems (LMS) can automate processes like course grading and admissions processing. This allows staff members to concentrate more on strategic planning and students' engagement (Guan et al., 2020; Lytras et al., 2024).

AI implementation in school management still witnesses some setback, despite the global trend. In Nigeria, some educational institutions still portend with AI challenges that are frequently not effective and prone to data loss. According to studies by Igbokwe, (2023) and Fabunmi et al., (2025), Nigerian institutions are becoming more interested in utilizing smart technology, especially for administrative reporting, e-learning platforms, and students' record management. These studies however draw attention to enduring issues including inadequate digital infrastructure, shortage of skilled workers and lack of legislative frameworks that facilitate the incorporation of AI. Furthermore, unequal access to financing, training, and scalable technical solutions exacerbates the digital gap between developed and underdeveloped nations (Assefa, 2024; Ayanwale et al., 2024; Ogunode et al., 2023). Meanwhile, nations with strong technology ecosystems quickly increase their AI capabilities in higher education. Whereas, it is important that institutions should geared towards having structural development through investing on capacity-building, digital infrastructure, and collaborating with international technology partners to adopt and modify AI solutions into their institutional local needs (Salloum et al., 2024; Meng et al., 2022).

THE ROLES OF AI IN REVOLUTIONIZING TERTIARY EDUCATION MANAGEMENT

The following are the roles of AI in the revolutionizing of tertiary education management:

Administrative Efficiency

Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to greatly increase administrative efficiency in higher education by automating a variety of time-consuming and repetitive operations (Ayanwale et al., 2024). Intelligent technologies can simplify tasks that are frequently complicated by human mistake and bureaucratic hold-ups, like student registration, transcript processing, exam scheduling and students' fee supervision (Bhardwaj & Sudan, 2024). Organizations may accelerate service delivery, guarantee more accuracy in record keeping and lower the risk of human error by utilizing AI-powered automation (Muggleton, 2014). While AI algorithms can optimize exam schedules and resource distribution using real-time data (Zhang & Aslan, 2021). In addition to increasing operational effectiveness, this automation frees up administrative personnel to concentrate on more valuable and strategic tasks like academic planning, student involvement and institutional development. Incorporating AI into administrative processes may result in more student-centered, transparent and responsive management techniques in higher education institutions.

Data-Driven Decision Making

Tertiary institution administrators should obtain important real-time insights into critical operational areas including staff efficiency, resources usage and student success by utilizing AI-powered analytics (Abdelkader et al., 2024). Using AI to combine and analyze data from different departments in an institution, this AI system help decision-makers to spot patterns, irregularities and implement evidence-based actions in the institution (Albalushi et al., 2024). AI can track academic records and identify students who are at risk of dropping out from schooling and allowing for quick academic support and counseling (Wang et al., 2024). In a similar vein, information about employee productivity and workloads can help with performance reviews and human resource planning. A subfield of artificial intelligence called predictive analytics helps organizations to make better decisions by predicting future trends (Shafiq, 2025). Predictive models can be use by institutions to forecast higher demand courses, assess student enrollment trends and adjust resource planning and budgeting accurately (Wong et al.,

2020). This proactive strategy ensures that institutions may successfully adjust to shifting educational demands and resource constraints by supporting strategic planning in addition to improving operational efficiency.

Personalized Student Support

AI chatbots and virtual assistants are transforming students' support services offering 24 hours access to administrative assistance, students' services and academic advising. These smart technologies can respond to frequently asked queries, help students select courses during registration, and promptly remind students of event dates (Fabunmi et al., 2025). AI-powered systems can provide initial mental health support in addition to academic support by connecting students with the campus resources and offering self-help materials (Ayanwale et al., 2024). Regardless of time zones and office hours, this technology guaranteed continuous support for students in their institutions. AI chatbots can create a more responsive and encouraging learning environment by cutting down on waiting times and making it easier to obtain necessary information and services (Al Balushi et al., 2024). AI incorporation into educational systems improves the general student experience, fosters wellbeing and ensure satisfaction, all of which can result in better academic performance (Fabunmi et al., 2025).

Quality Assurance and Accreditation

Fundamentally, to improve compliance with regulatory criteria established by organizations like the National Universities Commission (NUC), artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to revolutionize the data gathering and analysis procedures necessary for institutional accreditation (Olowoselu, 2024). In preparing for accreditation exercise, there is need for the provision of information on academic programs, staff credentials, research output, student demographics, infrastructure and staff development records in the institution. This procedure takes long time and is prone to mistakes and inconsistencies. The AI system automatically combined and validated these data and ensure compliant with accreditation standards (Quang & Nguyen, 2022). AI may also produce thorough reports, point out areas that want development and offer practical insights to areas of adjustments in the institution. AI further helps institution to stay prepared for accreditation processes by enabling real-time reporting and ongoing monitoring, which lessens the administrative loads on employees. This accreditation outcomes increased reputation in the higher education sector, create institutional transparency and effective compliance in the tertiary educational institutions (Olowoselu, 2024).

CHALLENGES TO AI ADOPTION IN NIGERIA TERTIARY EDUCATION

Nigeria's tertiary education system confronts numbers of challenges to implementing AI, despite its potential as outlined by (Olowoselu, 2024; Ogunode et al., 2023; Fabunmi et al., 2025).

Infrastructure Deficits: Lack of infrastructure, especially the unstable electrical supply interferes with digital learning environments and it is a significant obstacle in AI integration in higher education. The challenge is exacerbated by limited broadband connection, which makes it challenging institution to implement cloud-based platforms and real-time data processing tools that are necessary for AI capabilities. These challenges limit the use of smart technologies and increases digital divide, particularly for institutions located in rural areas.

Skills Gap: There is lack of AI specialists in who possess the technical knowledge required to promote AI integration in higher education. The application of intelligence systems is restricted, local creativity is diminished. The nation runs the risk of challenges in developing AI workforce, equipped to support and maintain AI-driven transformation in the education sector.

Funding Constraints: The majority of public tertiary institutions have tight finances, which significantly limits their capacity to fund initiatives aimed at digital transformation, including the integration of AI. Tertiary institutions find it difficult to

implement AI technologies that could improve operations and educational outcomes due to lack of fund for software procurement, infrastructure upgrades, and training initiatives.

Data Privacy and Ethics: Concerns of algorithmic bias, data security and privacy are imperative that need to be resolved as AI is incorporated into Nigeria's higher education system. It is pertinent to have strong regulations that guarantee data privacy of the individual against data abuse. Educational institutions should include ethical standards that emphasize accountability, transparency and fairness during implementation of AI applications in schools in order to guarantee data privacy and protection of staff and students.

SOLUTIONS TO PROPER MANAGEMENT OF AI IN TERTIARY EDUCATION

The following are solutions to the proper management of AI's potential in tertiary education in Nigeria:

1. It is pertinent to create policy framework that includes standards, ethical principles and implementation strategies for the National AI Policy on Education.
2. Development of capacity building for training programs for administrators, teachers and IT professionals to develop AI technical expertise.
3. Involvement of public-private partnerships to provide infrastructure and tools for collaboration with international technology companies.
4. Implement frequent AI training design to improve staff and students abilities in AI technologies.

CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence has the potential to completely transform and revolutionize Nigerian tertiary education management system. AI also has the potential to spur efficiency, accountability and creativity in a variety of ways, including the automation of administrative duties, the improvement of strategic planning and improvement of student services. However, cross-sector cooperation, including policymaking and proactive investment are necessary for its success. Nigeria can overcome long-standing challenges in its educational system and position its institutions at the forefront of global educational innovation by strategically adopting AI in all the tertiary institutions.

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